

Irony processing within a linguistic framework: a corpus-based theoretical analysis

Processamento de ironia em uma perspectiva linguística: uma análise teórica baseada em corpus

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ABSTRACT: Figurative (or nonliteral) language presents a persistent challenge for researchers in different scientific fields, ranging from linguistics to philosophy and psychology. Its intricate nature, particularly evident in phenomena like irony, has led scholars to outline hypotheses and theories that could potentially account for its complexity and specificity. Early attempts to explain ironic meaning through a linguistic (and, more specifically, pragmatic) lens included H.P. Grice's theory of conversational implicature, according to which listeners or readers have to first process an utterance's literal meaning to subsequently access and process its opposite non-literal meaning. Following Grice's account, dubbed the "literal-first" model (Sperber; Wilson, 2012, p. 125), an addressee would access the nonliteral meaning of a given utterance only if the utterance's literal meaning is in contradiction with the communicative context. Dissatisfaction with the Gricean model led to the formulation of influential alternative theories, such as Sperber and Wilson's (1981; 1992; 1995) "relevance theory", which emphasizes the notion of "second-degree interpretation" in irony processing, Gibbs's (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) "direct access view", which argues that ironic meaning may be processed before literal meaning, and Giora's (2002) "graded salience hypothesis", whose foundation is the degree of salience of a given meaning, which would further dictate processing order and cost. Although these theories may seem, at first glance, contradictory, and diverge largely in terms of the emphasis they concede to a listener's or reader's interpretation, the role the degree of familiarity plays in irony processing, and whether irony processing requires further cognitive effort in comparison to literal language, we argue that they share much common ground and may even be

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complementary in their respective assertions. Thus, rather than continuing to frame these theories as oppositional, this article advocates for a reassessment of their potential as complementary frameworks, which may shed further light on the nature and processing of irony. To that end, we provide a concise literature review of the four theories identified, outlining their main underlying assumptions, followed by an approximation among them, highlighting possible points of convergence. To illustrate our theoretical stance with empirical data, we conducted a small-scale qualitative corpus analysis using EPIC (Frenda *et al.*, 2023), a corpus of short online conversational exchanges composed of parent posts and replies. Replies were independently annotated by evaluators from different English-speaking countries and classified as ironic or non-ironic. This study is expected to contribute to the scientific understanding of figurative language from a pragmalinguistic and psycholinguistic standpoint.

KEYWORDS: Irony. Irony processing. Figurative language. Pragmatics.

RESUMO: A linguagem figurada (ou não literal) apresenta um desafio persistente para pesquisadores de diferentes campos científicos, que vão da linguística à filosofia e à psicologia. Sua natureza hermética, particularmente evidente em fenômenos como a ironia, levou pesquisadores a formularem hipóteses e teorias capazes de dar conta de sua complexidade e especificidade. Uma das primeiras tentativas de explicar o fenômeno da ironia através de uma perspectiva linguística (e, mais especificamente, pragmática) foi a teoria da implicatura conversacional de H. P. Grice, segundo a qual ouvintes processam, primeiramente, o sentido literal antes de inferir o sentido oposto, não literal, de um enunciado. Segundo a teoria de Grice, tida como o “modelo do ‘literal primeiro’” (Sperber; Wilson, 2012, p. 125, tradução nossa), o receptor apenas acessa o sentido não literal de um dado enunciado se o sentido literal do enunciado contradizer o contexto comunicativo. Considerando a teoria de Grice como insatisfatória, teóricos formularam teorias alternativas influentes, como a “teoria da relevância” (Sperber; Wilson, 1981; 1992; 1995), que enfatiza a noção da “interpretação de segundo grau” no processamento de ironia, “a visão do acesso direto” (Gibbs, 1983; 1989; 1994; 2002), que celebrenemente argumenta que o significado irônico pode ser processado antes do significado literal, e “a hipótese da saliência gradativa” (Giora, 2002), cuja base é o grau de saliência de um dado

significado, que, por sua vez, prescreveria a ordem e o custo de processamento. Embora tais teorias possam, à primeira vista, parecer contraditórias e divergirem amplamente no que tange à ênfase que concedem à interpretação do ouvinte ou leitor, ao papel desempenhado pela familiaridade no processamento de ironia e à questão da necessidade de esforço cognitivo adicional para o processamento de ironia em comparação à linguagem literal, argumentamos que elas compartilham pontos convergentes e podem até mesmo ser complementares em suas respectivas formulações. Logo, em vez de continuar considerando essas teorias como opostas, este artigo defende uma reapreciação de seu potencial enquanto referenciais complementares, passíveis de lançar luz sobre a natureza e o processamento da ironia. Para este fim, articulamos uma breve revisão bibliográfica a respeito das quatro teorias elencadas e, na sequência, realizamos uma aproximação entre elas, salientando suas respectivas convergências. Para ilustrar nossa posição teórica com dados empíricos, realizamos uma análise qualitativa de corpus em pequena escala utilizando o EPIC (Frenda *et al.*, 2023), um corpus de trocas conversacionais on-line curtas, composto por postagens iniciais e respostas. As respostas foram anotadas de forma independente por avaliadores de diferentes países de língua inglesa e classificadas como irônicas ou não irônicas. Estima-se contribuir, com o presente estudo, para o corpus científico a respeito da linguagem figurada através de uma perspectiva pragmalinguística e psicolinguística.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Ironia. Processamento de ironia. Linguagem figurada. Pragmática.

Introduction

Imagine meeting someone in an elevator after leaving your apartment. As you both approach the first floor, the elevator doors open to reveal a heavy thunderstorm. “What a lovely day!”, says your friendly neighbor as he crosses the elevator sill. This is a classic example of the use of irony as a linguistic device and as a means of conveying a meaning that opposes the semantic content of a sentence. Unless the speaker openly enjoys stormy days and the addressee is aware of this, the latter would most likely

interpret this remark as ironic in nature. But what types of contextual cues may lead the addressee to draw such an assumption?

Irony plays a significant role in the way we socialize, allowing us to maintain social relationships (Gibbs, 1994). Fabry (2021) considers that ironic utterances may be used to tease or criticize other people or to communicate emotions and feelings. Through a pragmatic lens, irony comprehension can be seen as “a process of disentangling surface utterances and their implied meanings” (Fabry, 2021, p. 6456). As such, irony processing involves “pragmalinguistic, social, and emotional component processes” that interact with one another (Fabry, 2021, p. 6456). In a study analyzing sixty-two ten-minute conversations between college students, it has been pointed out that irony makes up 8% of all conversational turns (Gibbs, 2000).

In another experimental study, Deliens *et al.* (2018) sought to investigate the role contextual cues may play in irony comprehension, concluding that ironic utterances often bear non-contextual cues that may help the receiver grasp its meaning. Irony is most plausibly construed through pragmatic inference, arising when the hearer detects an incongruity between the utterance’s literal meaning and the contextual cues surrounding its production. Moreover, “in one sense or another, all ironically intended messages deliberately mismatch the utterance's literal content” (Deliens *et al.*, 2018, p. 35). Thus, identifying and decoding an ironic utterance’s meaning would entail perceiving an existing contrast between the context in which the utterance is created and the utterance’s literal content. Such an assumption is in line with some considerations Sperber and Wilson (1981, p. 301) draw on “Irony and the Use-Mention Distinction”, in which they argue that “ironical utterances are not always distinguishable by intonation from their literal counterparts”. Faced with this lack of additional cues, an addressee would most likely have to rely on “information external to the utterance – contextual knowledge and other background assumptions – rather than the form or content of the utterance itself” (Sperber; Wilson, 1981, p. 301).

H. Paul Grice’s (1975) theory of conversational implicature offered one of the earliest pragmatic frameworks for understanding nonliteral language, establishing a foundation for its study within pragmatic research. Conversational implicature can be defined as “any meaning or proposition expressed implicitly by a speaker in his or her utterance of a sentence which is meant without being part of what is said in the strict

sense” (Huang, 2017, p. 156). While Grice’s (1975) primary focus was not the analysis of irony or nonliteral language per se, his considerations on implicature provided the groundwork for understanding irony from a linguistic perspective.

A central notion in Grice’s theory of conversational implicature is that utterances automatically raise expectations that “guide the addressee to infer what is conversationally implicated by the speaker” (Huang, 2017, p. 156). Grice conceived these expectations based upon the cooperative principle and its constituent maxims (Huang, 2017). However, it is worth noting that a conversational implicature cannot be considered an inference in itself; it is the addressee that formulates inferences about what the speaker has said, and such inferences may be considered successful or not depending on what the speaker aimed to convey through their utterance(s). In terms of irony processing, one of the basic assumptions underlying the Gricean model is that nonliteral language openly flouts the maxim of Quality – i.e., “do not say anything you believe to be false or for which you lack adequate evidence” (Gibbs, 2017, p. 316).

The Gricean account of irony processing has been challenged by different scholars across various disciplines, who mainly criticized its limitation as an analytical tool for real-world utterances. One prominent example is the American psychologist Raymond Gibbs (1994, p. 359), who describes the traditional definition of irony “as a situation that contrasts what is expected with what occurs or as a statement that contradicts the actual attitude of the speaker.” Gibbs (2017, p. 317) states that the classic Gricean model “is simply not an accurate reflection of what people ordinarily do when interpreting figurative language”. In a similar vein, Wilson (2017, p. 100) considers that Grice’s account of irony “sheds no light” on the correlation between irony comprehension and the ability to cope with deliberate deception and its reflection on second-order false belief tasks.

The perceived insufficiency or inadequacy of the Gricean model for explaining irony comprehension led linguists across various subfields to formulate their own accounts on irony processing. The “standard pragmatic view”, often linked to Grice’s view of irony as flouting the maxim of Quality, has been challenged by Wilson and Sperber’s (1981; 1992) “relevance theory”, Gibbs’s (2002) “direct access view” and Giora’s (2002) “graded salience hypothesis”. Others have chosen to follow a neo-Gricean path, such as Clark and Gerrig (1984) and, more recently, Sullivan (2019). Whilst much

effort is put into disallowing or rebuking the principles underlying the “standard pragmatic approach” in these newer perspectives on irony comprehension, we argue that they also reveal points of convergence. Indeed, it is undeniable that each approach, theory, view, or hypothesis on irony has its different aspects, but they also point to similar directions and may complement each other in such a way that may help us understand more about the complex phenomenon that is irony.

The main purpose of the present article is to articulate an examination of different linguistic theories and frameworks — largely pragmatics and psycholinguistics — on the processing, nature, and understanding of irony, drawing connections between them, highlighting their shared aspects, and illustrating their potential for mutual reinforcement. Moving beyond the notion that these theories are simply opposite and not complementary, we argue that they may, when taken together, help us understand the complex phenomenon of irony.

Further, while the present study is primarily theoretical in nature, it also incorporates a corpus-based qualitative analysis with the aim of illustrating the case that all theories may prove to be valid and efficient to analyze irony in different contexts. For the purposes of this article, we draw on the *English Perspectivist Irony Corpus* (EPIC; Frenda *et al.*, 2023), a dataset of online conversational exchanges taken from Reddit and X (formerly Twitter) assessed for irony by multiple independent annotators. Instead of pre-selecting ironic statements, EPIC presents irony as a reader-dependent judgement. The corpus is herein used to identify instances in which irony perception has been relatively stable across annotators, and only replies considered ironic by $\geq 75\%$ of annotators were considered, thus including only statements that potentially convey ironic meaning. For the purposes of this article, five segments were analyzed in light of the theories discussed.

1 Pragmalinguistic and psycholinguistic approaches to irony processing

Irony has been a topic of interest in a range of different scientific domains. From philosophy to neurolinguistics, the methods, approaches, and techniques employed to analyze irony are as variable as its uses and functions in everyday communication. Recent empirical studies have employed event-related potentials (ERPs), eye-tracking, and

functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to analyze on-site irony processing in different clinical and non-clinical populations (see Caffara *et al.*, 2019; Filik *et al.*, 2014). These technologies have shown that much of what had been previously theorized about irony comprehension is not reflected in on-site, experimental studies, which, in turn, led scholars to attempt to reformulate some classic approaches to irony comprehension (Gibbs, 2002).

In this section, we present the main approaches to irony comprehension or irony processing in the field of pragmatics and psycholinguistics: the Gricean (1975) model or “standard pragmatic view”, Sperber and Wilson’s (1981; 1995) “relevance theory”, Gibbs’s (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) “direct access view” and Giora’s (2002) “graded salience hypothesis”.

1.1 The Gricean model and the relevance theory hypothesis

When discussing the pragmatic notion of “implicature”, Huang (2007) cites the following example: “Chomsky is a great sociolinguist.” Anyone familiar with Chomskyan concepts and/or basic linguistic notions knows that such an utterance conveys a false information, given that “Chomsky is no sociolinguist at all” (Huang, 2007, p. 29). In uttering this sentence, the speaker would be openly flouting Grice’s (1975) maxim of Quality, according to which a speaker should be truthful in his utterance, refraining from making assertions that one believes to be false or for which one lacks sufficient evidence (Huang, 2007). To preserve the principle of cooperation – that is, the assumption that participants engaged in a communicative context will make their contributions as relevant as possible to the objective of the interaction –, the addressee would have to presuppose that the speaker is openly conveying a false utterance and thus providing an ironic reading “opposite to the literal meaning of the sentence” (Huang, 2007, p. 30).

Grice’s (1975) view of verbal irony as flouting the maxim of Quality has been considered part of what is called the “standard pragmatic view” on irony comprehension (Fabry, 2021). Following Grice’s perspective (1975), verbal irony contradicts the literal meaning of an utterance. The standard pragmatic view posits that nonliteral utterances are first processed by analyzing their complete literal meaning (Gibbs, 2002). Thus,

interpreting and processing them as nonliteral would require further cognitive processing, which would be activated only if the utterance content contradicts the communicative context. In this sense, both literal and nonliteral utterances would be initially interpreted literally. Wilson and Sperber (2012, p. 124) summarize Grice's approach as follows: "Grice's account is generally taken to imply a two-stage processing model in which the literal meaning of an utterance has to be tested and rejected before a figurative interpretation is considered".

This model has been increasingly questioned in the literature, as experimental studies show that nonliteral interpretations may be as cognitively effortful as literal ones, in contradiction to what Wilson and Sperber (2012, p. 124) dubbed "the 'literal-first' model". According to these authors, one of the main issues with Grice's model on irony comprehension is that it implicitly considers figurative utterances as unnecessary, given that, following a Gricean approach, the idea they convey could be transmitted by uttering their literal counterparts (Wilson; Sperber, 2012). Thus, in accordance with the "literal-first" model, "metaphor and irony should cost more to process than their literal counterparts, but yield no extra benefit, which makes their use irrational and a waste of effort" (Wilson; Sperber, 2012, p. 125). As a counterpart to the standard view of the Gricean model, Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1995) formulated their own theory regarding irony comprehension. The "relevance theory", as it came to be known, aimed to answer questions that had been, until then, left untouched by prior linguistic approaches to irony (Sperber; Wilson, 1981; 1992; 1995). Challenging the assumption that irony is a fixed concept with fixed characteristics, the authors suggest that utterances may be more or less loosely interpreted as ironical. They argue that "we should be looking for psychological mechanisms that can account for [the particular] effects [produced by particular utterances] and their interrelationships" (Sperber; Wilson, 1981, p. 298).

Sperber and Wilson (1981) go as far as to reject the notion of "figurative meaning" altogether, claiming that every utterance could be considered ambiguous in itself. The problem of ambiguity further complicates the interpretation of utterances, but Sperber and Wilson (1981) consider the notion of conversational implicature as relevant to the disambiguation process. In a later contribution (Sperber; Wilson, 1995), they suggest that it is solely a second-degree interpretation – i.e., an inference about the thoughts of a speaker when conveying a given utterance, what has also been dubbed as "second-order

theory of mind” – that creates the ironic content, since the interpretation of a speaker’s thought “is always, in the first place, an interpretation of one’s understanding of that other person’s thought” (Sperber; Wilson, 1995, p. 238). Referring to the focus on their theory, Sperber and Wilson (1995) state that a speaker’s interpretation of a thought is relevant in itself. The basis of the authors’ premises is that ironic utterances are cases of echoic interpretation.

Echoic utterances can be considered a means by which an addressee conveys to a speaker that they have been paying attention to what was said. They can assume the form of repetitions or mere echoes of a person’s thoughts. In the authors’ words,

By representing someone’s utterance, or the opinions of a certain type of person, or popular wisdom, in a manifestly skeptical, amused, surprised, triumphant, approving or reproving way, the speaker can express her own attitude to the thought echoed, and the relevance of her utterance might depend largely on this expression of attitude. Sometimes, the speaker’s attitude is left implicit, to be gathered only from tone of voice, context and other paralinguistic clues; at other times it may be made explicit (Sperber; Wilson, 1995, p. 239).

Sperber and Wilson (1995, p. 239) further argue that verbal irony involves the “implicit expression of an attitude” whose relevance depends on what it conveys regarding “the speaker’s attitude to the opinion echoed”. These attitudes may range from agreement and disagreement to outright disapproval. However, according to the authors, an ironic utterance invariably conveys a rejection or disapproval, for, in uttering an ironic statement, “the speaker dissociates herself from the opinion echoed and indicates that she does not hold it herself” (Sperber; Wilson, 1995, p. 239).

1.2 The direct access view and the graded salience hypothesis: cognitive contributions to irony processing comprehension

In his introduction to irony as a linguistic phenomenon, Gibbs revisits Kierkegaard’s statement that “as philosophers claim that no true philosophy is possible without doubt, by the same token, one may claim that no authentic human life is possible without irony” (*apud* Gibbs, 1994, p. 359-360). Contextualizing Kierkegaard’s formulation, Gibbs (1994, p. 359-360) argues that the use of irony in everyday human communication stems from the conceptualization of various everyday experiences in terms of irony, which “may be our most powerful weapon in everyday speech: a device

for concealing our true intentions, for avoiding responsibility for what we say, or for turning the world or oneself inside out”.

Gibbs’s (1983; 1994) considerations on the processing of irony contradicted much of what had been theorized beforehand. Gibbs (1994) challenged the Gricean conception of irony, which holds that verbal irony stands in contradiction to the literal meaning of a sentence. As previously shown, according to the standard pragmatic view, to be successfully processed and decoded, an ironic utterance would first be processed by accessing its full literal content. Therefore, further processing would be required to access its nonliteral content. However, the direct access view suggests that nonliteral utterances do not always require that people “first analyze their literal meanings before deriving their conveyed meanings” (Gibbs, 1983, p. 524).

Gibbs (2002) formulated arguments in favor of a psycholinguistic view on irony in a recent contribution, titled “A new look at literal meaning in understanding what is said and implicated.” Although the very notion of “implicature” is explicitly conveyed in the title of his article, much of Gibbs’s (2002, p. 458) efforts are drawn towards a critique of the “standard pragmatic view”: “I have been critical of theories that assume listeners/readers must first analyze the literal meanings of utterances before applying pragmatic information to derive what speakers implicate.” His main point of divergence in relation to Grice’s theory on nonliteral language processing is that the literal meaning always has to be processed first. To formally respond to the standard pragmatic view, Gibbs (2002, p. 458) suggests “people often appear to directly understand what speakers intend to communicate when using figurative language without having to process the literal meanings of speakers’ utterances”.

Gibbs (2002, p. 459) further argues that psycholinguistic experiments have shown that Grice’s view on figurative language is not accurate and has “little psychological validity”, for listeners or readers can understand nonliteral language – e.g., idioms, metaphors, sarcasm, irony, and so on – without having to reject their literal meanings first. Thus, the main point of divergence between Gibbs’s direct access view and the standard pragmatic view is that the former considers that listeners/readers do not always have to rely on literal processing first in order to comprehend a figurative meaning within a given utterance or sentence. In Gibbs’s (2002, p. 460) words, “the direct access view simply claims that listeners need not automatically analyze the complete literal meanings

of linguistic expressions before accessing pragmatic knowledge to figure out what speakers mean to communicate”.

A convincing argument put forward by Gibbs (2002) is that the analysis of an utterance’s complete literal content implies a highly non-pragmatic perspective. However, he clarifies that the direct access view does not reject the claim that individuals may access the meaning of the individual words altogether or presupposes that they might never take less time to process a figurative meaning than a literal one. Rather, the direct access view posits that “people do not automatically analyze the complete context-free, or literal meanings, of entire utterances before deriving their figurative meanings” (Gibbs, 2002, p. 461).

Rachel Giora (2002) proposed yet a fourth view on irony processing. Based on the assumption that neither the standard pragmatic model nor the direct access is entirely consistent with experimental findings, Giora (2002, p. 490) suggests we consider a “graded salience hypothesis”, which posits the priority of salient (coded, context-independent, prominent) meanings.

As one might infer, Giora’s (2002) model is based upon the notion of “salience”. According to the author, the meanings of words or expressions can be more or less salient, a gradation that applies effectively to polysemous words. For example, the word “bank” has two potential meanings: a financial institution and the land alongside a river or lake. In capitalist societies, the first meaning may be more salient than the latter, whereas in agricultural societies, the second meaning might be more salient in comparison to the first. The meaning of salient words must be coded in the mental lexicon, and a word may be more or less prominent due to its conventionality, frequency, familiarity, and prototypicality (see Giora, 2002, p. 490). Nevertheless, a familiar, formulaic ironic expression — e.g., “very funny”, “a fine friend” — can have two salient meanings: one literal and one ironic (Giora, 2002). In a psycholinguistic perspective, salient meanings, as soon as conveyed in a linguistic stimulus, are accessed immediately via the mental lexicon, whereas nonsalient meanings would require further investigation to be processed and comprehended. In sum,

The graded salience hypothesis [...] assumes that, at the initial access phase, literal and nonliteral utterances should not vary processing-wise; they should reveal the salient meaning(s) initially, regardless of contextual information or literality. Only when salient meanings are contextually incompatible are

additional processes or a strong context required. The distinction, then, that best predicts processing differences is not the literal/figurative divide, but the salient-nonsalient continuum (Giora, 2002, p. 492).

According to Giora (2002), only the graded salience hypothesis can explain experimental results that differentiate tropes by their salience. This contrasts with the standard pragmatic and direct access views, which propose that early processing is determined by context and (non)literality, respectively. Giora's (2002) view prioritizes salience in the initial processing stage, shifting the focus from literal or nonliteral interpretation to meaning salience.

2 Converging in divergence: an approximation of the different linguistic accounts on irony processing and comprehension

Despite the fact that scholars from various fields of knowledge have addressed figurative language from a range of different – and at times diverging – perspectives, it remains a topic investigated and discussed in scholarly literature. Irony, as an example of figurative language, is not an exception: as Filik *et al.* (2024, p. 811) point out, “little is known about how people process and understand [irony]”. Much of the previous effort in research on irony was directed to reformulating Grice's standard view on nonliteral language comprehension.

Indeed, Grice's (1975) conversational implicature theory has significantly shaped linguistic research on irony processing, although it is surely not its focus. Despite attempts by scholars from different linguistic fields to offer alternative perspectives, the central point of contention appears to be the dichotomy between literal and nonliteral meaning. This leads to questions about processing order and priority: when an utterance has both literal and nonliteral potential meanings, which one is accessed first? Is the literal meaning more readily apparent and thus processed before the nonliteral one? Is irony — or, for that matter, any sort of figurative language or trope — processing more cognitively effortful than literal language processing, given it would require further processing? Do factors like relevance, context, or salience affect this initial stage of cognitive processing?

To answer these and other questions, authors sought to draft their own respective theories on the nature of irony and its processing, always attempting to debunk previous considerations on the topic. It is not surprising that much effort has been deployed to

rebuke Grice's (1975) account of irony, given his considerations were pioneering in the field of pragmatics and, consequently, figurative language processing. The continuous engagement with his work evidences the foundational importance of his concept of conversational implicature in the study of irony processing.

As previously asserted, one of the first accounts to challenge Grice's perspective on irony comprehension was outlined by Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1995). Instead of assuming that literal meaning is inherently processed before nonliteral meaning, Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1995) argue that it is the principle of relevance that guides language processing. This means that, when faced with a given utterance, addressees seek the interpretation requiring the least cognitive effort for the greatest accuracy – i.e., the “most relevant” interpretation. Their theory provides a more nuanced understanding of irony, suggesting that ironic meaning is not always in opposition to literal meaning, but can often be the echoic expression of disapproval or rejection towards a widely held or shared belief³. Despite these specific differences regarding the nature and processing of irony, Sperber and Wilson's (1981; 1995) approach fundamentally aligns with Grice's (1975). Both theories share a focus on the speaker's intention and the addressee's reception and interpretation of the speaker's intention. Another evident point of congruence is the fact that both Grice (1975) and Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1992; 1995) consider the context in which a sentence is uttered, which is ultimately essential in a pragmatic analysis.

It is worth noting that, although Sperber and Wilson (1992) do not reject Grice's perspective altogether, they consider it to be limited in scope. They point out that not all ironic utterances can be adequately explained in terms of implicature derived from a violation of conversational maxims or from a simple opposition between literal and intended meaning.

In Sperber and Wilson's view, verbal irony always presents an inherent disapproval. In this sense, a speaker may echo a thought they attribute to someone else and convey their disapproval of that thought. However, the thought echoed may not be attributable to a specific person, but to a group of people that share this same thought or even to a “cultural aspiration or norm” (Sperber; Wilson, 1992, p. 60). Moreover, an

³ To echo a thought or utterance is to utter a similar content, to express a critical or mocking attitude to it (Wilson, 2006).

echoic utterance may not present the exact words previously mentioned by someone; it can be paraphrastic or an exaggeration, a caricature of what was said.

In turn, Gibbs's (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) considerations on nonliteral language follow a more openly cognitive and psycholinguistic framework. Apparently, his main point of disagreement with Grice's perspective of irony as flouting the maxim of Quality stems from the assumption that nonliteral language is always more cognitively effortful to process than literal language. Nonetheless, Gibbs does not completely reject Grice's perspective, as he contends that some examples of figurative language can be as effortless – or effortful – to process as literal language. The direct access view diverges from the standard pragmatic model mostly in terms of what Sperber and Wilson dubbed as “literal-first” processing. To Gibbs, the literal meaning is not necessarily processed first. In summary, “if context supports an ironic interpretation, this can be activated directly, with no need for the literal interpretation to be accessed first” (Filik *et al.*, 2014, p. 811). Gibbs's direct access view functions primarily as a corrective to Gricean assumptions about processing order, rather than as an independent analytical framework for diagnosing different types of ironic utterances.

This perspective leads us to the last hypothesis considered in the present article. Giora's (2002) graded salience hypothesis seems to be the most corroborated in the scientific literature, predominantly in experimental studies using eye-tracking, ERPs, and neuroimaging (see Filik; Moxey, 2010; Spotorno *et al.*, 2013; Filik *et al.*, 2014). Giora's (2002) hypothesis is based upon the notion that the salient meaning of a word or expression is processed first. This salient meaning is not necessarily the literal one. Depending on the familiarity and prototypicality of an ironic expression, for example, its figurative meaning may be more salient than its literal one. Thus, in this case, the processing of the ironic meaning would be less cognitively effortful and more readily accessible in comparison to the literal meaning.

Gibbs's (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) and Giora's (2002) approaches share several crucial common grounds regarding irony processing. A more apparent agreement between the authors is the inaccuracy and insufficiency of one of the core tenets of the standard pragmatic view – i.e., the “literal-first” processing model – when dealing with figurative language, a viewpoint also shared by Sperber and Wilson. Secondly, Gibbs (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002), Giora (2002), and Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1995) seem to

deny the assumption that non-literal meaning is inherently more cognitively effortful to process in comparison to literal meaning, which does not mean, however, that it is always less cognitively effortful or as cognitively effortful. In Gibbs's perspective, it is a matter of general contextual support: it is the content that makes the intended meaning (literal or figurative) more readily accessible. In Giora's work, it is a matter of salience: the more salient meaning is the more readily apparent and thus more easily accessed and processed. In Filik *et al.*'s (2014, p. 811) words, the graded salience hypothesis "assumes that salient meanings and salience-based interpretations are activated initially".

Giora's model undeniably offer a more nuanced, context-sensitive account of irony processing. Scholars state that the graded salience hypothesis, for example, "can be seen as mediating between the standard pragmatic model and the direct access view" (Fabry, 2021, p. 6458). However, Filik *et al.* (2014, p. 812) seem to take the opposite stance, claiming that "the graded salience hypothesis gives a very limited role to the context in which a comment is uttered". This would contrast sharply with Gibbs's direct access view, for it attributes the accessibility of a meaning within an utterance to the context in which it is uttered. Thus, in Filik *et al.*'s (2014) interpretation, these two models would diverge significantly on the role of context.

To address this conundrum, it is worth recalling Giora's (2002) example of the word "bank" cited in the previous section: its "financial institution" meaning may be more salient in a capitalist society, while its "riverside" meaning is salient in an agricultural community. This example demonstrates that context indeed plays a role in determining the salience of a given meaning, which is, in itself, context-dependent. Contrary to Filik *et al.*'s (2014) assertion, we contend that the direct access view and the graded salience hypothesis share more points in common than differences, and that both theories rely on contextual information.

Further, a central point of disagreement between relevance theory and the graded salience hypothesis concerns the role of lexical meaning in irony recognition. Sperber and Wilson (1992, p. 62) argue that "irony [is] not recognizable from [its] linguistic form alone", but must be identified through pragmatic interpretation – i.e., via echoic attribution and dissociative attitude. Giora (2002), by contrast, maintains that some ironic interpretations can be accessed directly when they are lexically salient, insofar as salience

– determined by factors such as conventionality and familiarity – privileges certain meanings independently of inferential reconstruction.

As previously mentioned, experimental studies sought to apply tasks and tests to clinical and nonclinical populations to test the validity of the hypotheses put forward by scholars. In their study, Filik *et al.* (2014), for example, recorded participants' eye movements while reading and their electrical brain activity while listening to familiar and unfamiliar ironies, as well as non-ironic language. The main aim of Filik *et al.*'s (2014) study was to test theories on irony processing through eye-tracking and ERPs. Their results corroborate Giora's graded salience hypothesis, which seems to be the only linguistic account of irony that takes into consideration the degree of familiarity of ironic expressions. Similarly, Filik and Moxey (2010), as well as Spotorno *et al.* (2013), support Giora's hypothesis in their respective experimental studies. On the other hand, Balconi and Amenta's (2008) study, which also employed ERPs to analyze on-site irony processing, corroborates Gibbs's direct access view. Ivanko and Pexman's (2003) experimental study also supports Gibbs's account of irony processing.

In sum, it seems that irony processing is somehow dependent on context, meaning salience, relevance, and inference. Following Gibbs's view, an ironic meaning, if familiar and prototypical and thus readily apparent, may be less cognitively effortful to process and may be processed first, without the need to access a literal meaning. Moreover, in this sense, an ironic meaning may also be more salient than a literal meaning, which would also lead an addressee to access this ironic meaning first. The addressee might also interpret an ironic remark as an echoic utterance in which the speaker is conveying his disagreement or disavowal of a commonly shared belief or opinion. All these possibilities seem to coexist rather than cancel each other out. This emphasizes the necessity of experimental research on irony processing, as only through controlled empirical investigation can we advance our understanding of this complex cognitive phenomenon. It appears that, depending on the linguistic stimuli presented in a given experiment, one or another account of irony processing would be corroborated. What these theories on irony processing show us is that there may not be an absolute, undeniable truth to how irony is comprehended and processed. It all depends on the context in which it is uttered.

3 Irony as a reader-dependent judgement: a corpus-based analysis

As a means of illustrating our theoretical stance with real-world data, we conducted a small, corpus-based qualitative analysis using EPIC, a corpus of short online conversational exchanges in which each instance consists of a parent post and a reply (Frenda *et al.*, 2023). Each reply was assessed independently by annotators from different English-speaking countries, who, in turn, labeled the replies as ironic or non-ironic (Frenda *et al.*, 2023). EPIC was accessed via the Hugging Face dataset distribution. We used Python (version 3.14.2) to load the corpus locally and convert the file to a table format for inspection and filtering. It is worth noting that the same pair (i.e., parent post and reply) can appear multiple times, once per annotator, with a binary label (i.e., “iro” or “not”; Frenda *et al.*, 2023). Given that the number of annotations per segment is not uniform, with some segments having four, five, or six annotations, we decided to retain only segments that (i) had at least four annotations, and (2) were labeled “iro” by at least 75% of annotators. This method was chosen to minimize “borderline” cases.

Considering the limited scope of this article, five reply segments from the EPIC were selected (with their immediately preceding context, as provided in the datasets). We do not intend to present a comprehensive set of examples of ironic utterances, but to illustrate it in an authentic context and against the background of the four theoretical stances discussed in the previous sections. All segments were included exactly as they were written in the corpus, regardless of grammar/syntax errors.

Many examples lack prior context, which would be essential to grasp the ironic meaning in its entirety. Moreover, others are grounded on real-world prior knowledge, referencing external sources (video games, movies, bands, political subjects and so on). Therefore, to identify the ironic content, a reader would have to be acquainted with these external sources. Some instances also present *formulaic* examples of irony (i.e., structures that are commonly or almost directly associated with an ironic tone).

Above each parent text-reply pair, we indicate in parentheses the number of annotators who labeled the reply as ironic, specifying the degree of annotator agreement for each example.

(1) **parent_text:** *My son came home from a party (obviously drunk) he had to throw up and he said he was ill from the food.*

text: *your son is brilliant*

Labeled as ironic by three out of four annotators, the reply in (1) is a weakly marked instance of irony, as it does not rely on a formulaic ironic expression in Giora's (2002) sense. The adjective "brilliant" is used to refer to a clever, ingenious person, thing, or behavior, being canonically associated with a highly positive evaluation of intelligence. Thus, its ironic interpretation may not be lexically encoded. Instead, the ironic reading arises from the contrast between this positive evaluation and the contextual information, which is sufficient for most readers to converge on an ironic interpretation.

From a Gricean perspective, the literal meaning of "brilliant" would have to be accessed before its ironic meaning. But contextual information – in this case, the parent's remark –, when coupled with real-world prior knowledge, could account for the relative immediacy of the ironic interpretation. This is more naturally accommodated by perspectives that allow context to activate ironic interpretation early on. Gibbs's direct access view is compatible with this observation, for it allows the ironic meaning to be accessed without a "literal-first" stage. Nevertheless, it does not specify why the ironic interpretation should be privileged in the absence of conventionalized ironic marking.

Giora's (2002) hypothesis seems to offer a more nuanced explanation: the literal meaning of "brilliant", which is arguably the most salient one, is likely activated initially, but rapidly overridden in light of contextual mismatch. Following this account, irony emerges through the interaction between salient lexical meaning and contextual constraint.

(6/6)

(2) **parent_text:** *Epstein didn't kill himself, and how the Coronavirus magically trounced the Hong Kong protests.*

text: *Yes I'm sure that China decimated its entire country and economy to temporarily remove HK out of the news cycle (after the media had mostly gotten over it anyway)*

Unlike the weakly marked case in (1), the reply in (2), labeled as ironic by all six annotators, is a strongly marked, formulaic instance of irony. The ironic reading is supported by three converging cues: the over-exaggeration conveyed by "decimate its entire country and economy", the mock alignment introduced by "Yes I'm sure that", and the highly improbable causal relation expressed in the reply. Together with the conspiratorial framing of the parent post, these features make it unlikely that literal meaning would be entertained as a viable interpretation at any stage.

From a Gricean perspective, the ironic interpretation results from a deliberate violation of the maxim of Quality. However, while seemingly descriptively adequate, this account offers limited insight into why irony is perceived as immediate and why such an exaggerated formulation is chosen. If we analyze the reply as an echoic utterance that echoes the parent text's conspiratorial claim and simultaneously distances the speaker from the original reasoning, relevance theory seems to offer a more direct explanation. However, the graded salience hypothesis provides a particularly economical account for this case: given the conventionalized nature of mocking constructions such as "Yes, I'm sure that" in ironic discourse, the ironic meaning of the utterance is likely more salient than its literal counterpart. Irony would be accessed directly not because literal meaning is bypassed, but because it is pragmatically suppressed in favor of a more salient ironic interpretation.

(6/6)

(3) **parent_text:** *Finding Nemo. That shit was scary as fuck*

text: *Shat my pants only looking at the title, never scare me like that again man*

Interpreting (3) as ironic crucially depends on access to external source knowledge. *Finding Nemo* is a widely known animated film released by Pixar in 2002 and conventionally associated with child-friendly themes rather than fear or violence. In the absence of this cultural knowledge, neither the parent post nor the reply would necessarily trigger an ironic interpretation.

Although EPIC looks at irony only at the reply level, in this case, both the parent text and the reply can be interpreted as ironic. The exaggerated expressions "scary as fuck" and "shat my pants" are not inherently implausible; rather, their ironic tone arises

from the mismatch between these descriptions and the expectations associated with the film. The unanimous ironic judgements (6/6) therefore suggest that the annotators are acquainted with the film, allowing for rapid convergence on an ironic convergence.

In order to identify a violation of the maxim of Quality (Grice, 1975), the reader would have to supply substantial background assumptions, as the propositions expressed are not ironically marked per se. Given encyclopedic knowledge plays a central role in interpretation, the graded salience hypothesis offers limited explanatory foundation in this case. Example (3) highlights a class of ironic utterances grounded in extra-linguistic knowledge, whose interpretation depends less on lexical salience than on shared cultural reference.

(6/6)

(4) **parent_text:** *Your mum*

text: *Haven't heard that one before*

The expression “your mom” is a highly conventionalized insult in the English language, generally used as a humorous response to a question, either to bring laughter or to insult the speaker (Drange; Hasund; Stenström, 2014). In turn, the reply in (7) is also a formulaic ironic expression — i.e., “Haven’t heard that one before” — used, in this context, to express the unoriginality of an insult. There is little reason to assume that a reader would entertain the literal meaning of the reply, taking into account both (a) its salient ironic meaning, and (b) its contextual background — i.e., the parent text. In this sense, the ironic meaning would be accessed directly, without necessarily involving prior literal meaning processing.

While this pattern is compatible with Gibbs’s (2002) direct access view, Giora’s (2002) framework offers a more specific explanation of why direct access is possible in this case — namely, because the ironic meaning is already encoded in the mental lexicon and does not compete with a viable literal alternative. In Giora’s (2002) terms, this case exemplifies salience-driven irony: the ironic meaning of the reply is dominant, familiar, and readily accessible. The unanimous ironic judgements (6/6) further support this analysis, as it is expected in cases where irony is conveyed through conventionalized expressions with salient nonliteral meanings.

(4/5)

(5) **parent_text:** *How many years ago was 1951*

text: *Yeah that would be NICE to know*

Example (11) illustrates a weakly marked, interactional form of irony in which the ironic effect arises from pragmatic non-cooperation rather than from lexical incongruity or propositional falsity. Likely, the expected response to the question would either be (a) a number or (b) an assertion of lack of knowledge (e.g., “I don’t know”). However, the actual response contains an evaluative comment about the question itself, mirroring its absurdity, given that it would be easier to search for it than post it in a social media platform or public forum. The speaker pretends to align with what was said (“yeah”), then subtly withholds cooperation. There is no false proposition in Gricean terms. In terms of lexical meaning salience, “nice to know” does not have a conventionalized ironic meaning. Here, following relevance theory, we argue that the speaker presents a dissociative attitude towards the relevance of the question.

By employing multiple theoretical approaches – namely, Grice’s conversational implicature, Sperber and Wilson’s relevance theory, Gibbs’s direct access view, and Giora’s graded salience hypothesis – we propose that irony in utterances taken from the EPIC is best understood as a multifaceted phenomenon, with each framework highlighting a different explanatory aspect of ironic interpretation.

Final considerations

Although it has been thoroughly studied and theorized at least since ancient Greece (Colebrook, 2004), irony continues to be a topic of interest in contemporary research. From a linguistic standpoint, it has been subject to more diligent scrutiny since Grice (1975) formulated his theory of conversational implicature. Disagreements and disavowals soon followed, with theorists and researchers from a range of different fields attempting to formulate their hypotheses and theories on irony processing. This article aimed to revisit some of these theories and consider the points at which they converge instead of considering them as non-complementary.

Taken together, the four theories herein considered seem to share more similarities than incongruities. Although authors disagree mostly in terms of what is prevalent or not and whether a literal or nonliteral meaning is processed first or which is more costly in cognitive terms, the concepts of relevance and salience, for example, share much of the same ground. Gibbs's (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) direct access view draws largely upon Grice's (1975) conversational implicature theory. The same applies to Sperber and Wilson (1981; 1995), whose very theory stems from Gricean concepts. Gibbs's (1983; 1989; 1994; 2002) and Giora's (2002) perspectives are mostly complementary: the role the context plays in Gibbs's theory is basically replaced, in Giora's, by the notion of salience. However, Gibbs suggests that nonliteral language processing is as cognitively effortful as literal language processing, while Giora's hypothesis implies that nonliteral language may require further processing if the nonliteral meaning is less salient than the literal meaning of an utterance.

As reinforced by the corpus analyses, verbal irony is not a unitary phenomenon governed by a single interpretive mechanism. While Gricean, relevance-based, and salience-based accounts often converge on the resulting interpretation, they differ in the explanatory weight they attribute to lexical meaning, contextual information, and background knowledge. The EPIC data show that ironic meaning may arise from conventionalized expressions, contextual mismatch, evaluative over-application, or shared cultural reference, further suggesting no single theoretical framework can fully capture the range of ironic practices observed in natural discourse. Rather than competing explanations, these approaches appear to model complementary dimensions of irony comprehension. Irony comprehension does not draw on a single mechanism; rather, different ironic effects arise from different sources (lexical salience, contextual contrast, evaluative stance, cultural reference), and existing theories converge on interpretation while diverging in what they treat as central.

Although they share much of the same ground, it is worth noting that these theories do still present some disagreements, particularly in terms of the retainment of meaning during and after processing: the standard pragmatic view predicts that, during nonliteral language processing, the literal meaning is replaced by the nonliteral meaning, whereas the direct access view considers that the nonliteral meaning is processed at the same time. According to the graded salience hypothesis, both the literal and nonliteral meanings are

retained after processing, for the addressee must have access to both, given they are necessary to understand the figurative meaning (Filik & Moxey, 2010).

Most of the literature on irony processing has considered these four theories as contrasting, opposite, or non-complementary. Instead of following this same path, we chose to point out similarities and differences among these views so that they could, together, shed more light on the complex and fascinating phenomenon that is irony. We move beyond opposing accounts of irony by integrating similarities and differences across these four theories.

References

CAFFARRA, Sendy; HAERI, Arman Motamed; MICHELL, Elissa; MARTIN, Clara D. When is irony influenced by communicative constraints? ERP evidence supporting interactive models. **European Journal of Neuroscience**, v. 50, n. 10, p. 3566-77, jul. 2019. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.14503>. Acesso em: 10 out. 2025.

COLEBROOK, Claire. **Irony** (1st ed.). London: Routledge, 2004.
DELIENS, Gaétane; ANTONIOU, Kyriakos; CLIN, Elise; OSTASCHCHENKO, Ekaterina; KISSINE, Mikhail. Context, facial expression and prosody in irony processing. **Journal of Memory and Language**, v. 99, p. 35-48, apr. 2018. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2017.10.001>. Acesso em: 20 nov. 2025.

DRANGE, Eli-Marie Danbolt; HASUND, Ingrid Kristine; STENSTRÖM, Anna-Brita. “Your mum!?”: Teenagers’ swearing by mother in English, Spanish and Norwegian. **International Journal of Corpus Linguistics**, v. 19, n. 1, p. 29-59, jan. 2014. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1075/ijcl.19.1.02dra>. Acesso em: 06 jan. 2026.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. Do people always process the literal meanings of indirect requests? **Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition**, v. 9, n. 3, p. 524-533, 1983. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.9.3.524>. Acesso em: 22 out. 2025.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. Understanding and literal meaning. **Cognitive Science**, v. 13, n. 2, p. 243-251, apr. 1989. DOI [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-0213\(89\)90006-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-0213(89)90006-2). Acesso em: 17 out. 2025.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. Irony. In: GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. **The poetics of mind: figurative thought, language and understanding**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994, p. 359-398.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. Irony in talk among friends. **Metaphor and Symbol**, v. 15, n. 1-2, p. 5-27, 2000. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1080/10926488.2000.9678862>. Acesso em: 24 out. 2025.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. A new look at literal meaning in understanding what is said and implicated. **Journal of Pragmatics**, v. 34, n. 4, p. 457-486, 2002. DOI [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166\(01\)00046-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166(01)00046-7). Acesso em: 26 out. 2025.

GIBBS, Raymond W. Jr. Experimental Pragmatics. In: HUANG, Yan (ed.). **The Oxford Handbook of Pragmatics**. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017, p. 310-325.

GIORA, Rachel. Literal vs. figurative language: Different or equal? **Journal of Pragmatics**, v. 34, n. 4, p. 487-506, apr. 2002. DOI [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166\(01\)00045-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-2166(01)00045-5). Acesso em: 04 nov. 2025.

GRICE, H. Paul. Logic and conversation. In: COLE, Peter; MORGAN, Jerry L. (eds.). **Syntax and Semantics, Volume 3: Speech Acts**. Amsterdam: Academic Press, 1975, p. 41-58.

FABRY, Ragina E. Getting it: A predictive processing approach to irony comprehension. **Synthese**, v. 198, n. 3, p. 6455–6489, nov. 2019. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-019-02470-9>. Acesso em: 10 out. 2025.

FILIK, Ruth; LEUTHOLD, Harmut; WALLINGTON, Katie; PAGE, Jemma. Testing theories of irony processing using eye-tracking and ERPs. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, v. 40, n. 3, p. 811–828, 2014. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035658>. Acesso em: 30 nov. 2025.

FILIK, Ruth; MOXEY, Linda M. The on-line processing of written irony. **Cognition**, v. 116, n. 3, p. 421–436, sep. 2010. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2010.06.005>. Acesso em: 29 nov. 2025.

FRENDIA, Simona; PEDRANI, Alessandro; BASILE, Valerio; LO, Soda Marem; CIGNARELLA, Alessandra Teresa; PANIZZON, Raffaella; MARCO, Cristina; SCARLINI, Bianca; PATTI, Viviana; BOSCO, Cristina; BERNARDI, Davide. EPIC: Multi-Perspective Annotation of a Corpus of Irony. In: Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 61., 2023, Toronto. **Proceedings** [...]. Toronto: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2023. p. 13844-13857.

HUANG, Yan. Implicature. In: HUANG, Yan. **Pragmatics**. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007, p. 23-63.

HUANG, Yan. Implicature. In: HUANG, Yan (ed.). **The Oxford Handbook of Pragmatics**. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017, p. 155-179.

IVANKO, Stacey L.; PEXMAN, Penny M. Context incongruity and irony processing. **Discourse Processes**, v. 35, n. 3, p. 241–279, jun. 2010. DOI https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326950DP3503_2. Acesso em: 15 nov. 2025.

SPERBER, Dan; WILSON, Deirdre. Irony and the Use-Mention Distinction. In: COLE, Peter (ed.). **Radical Pragmatics**. Amsterdam: Academic Press, 1981, p. 295–318.

SPERBER, Dan; WILSON, Deidre. **Relevance: Communication & Cognition** (2nd ed.). Hoboken: Blackwell Publishers Ltd., 1995.

SPERBER, Dan; WILSON, Deidre. On verbal irony. **Lingua**, v. 87, n. 1-2, p. 53-76, jun. 1992. DOI [https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3841\(92\)90025-E](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3841(92)90025-E). Acesso em: 18 out. 2025.

SPOTORNO, Nicola; CHEYLUS, anne; VAN DER HENST, Jean-Baptiste; NOVECK, Ira A. What's behind a P600? Integration Operations during Irony Processing. **PLoS One**, v. 8, n. 6, e66839, jun. 2013. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066839>. Acesso em: 10 nov. 2025.

SULLIVAN, Arthur. The varieties of verbal irony: a new neo-Gricean taxonomy. **Lingua**, v. 232, 102740, dec. 2019. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2019.102740>. Acesso em: 14 nov. 2025.

WILSON, Deirdre. Relevance theory. In: HUANG, Yan (ed.). **The Oxford Handbook of Pragmatics**. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017, p. 79-100.

WILSON, Deirdre. The pragmatics of verbal irony: Echo or pretence? **Lingua**, v. 116, n. 10, p. 1722–1743, oct. 2006. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2006.05.001>. Acesso em: 18 out. 2025.

WILSON, Deirdre; SPERBER, Dan. Explaining irony. In: WILSON, Deirdre; SPERBER, Dan (eds.). **Meaning and Relevance**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012, p. 123–145.